

Living with Haru4Kids: Child and Parent Perceptions of a Co-Habitation Robot for Children *

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Abstract. *Haru4Kids* (H4K) is an app-based robot designed to co-habitate with children in their home. Seven families interacted with H4K for about two weeks each, and expressed their general feedback on the platform and their preferred activities with it, as well as their comfort levels with keeping H4K in different spaces of the home. Pre- and Post-interviews with at least one of the parents and all participating children allowed us to gauge familial comfort with sharing different kinds of information with the platform, and to assess how their experiences living with the robot changed their comfort levels. Children most preferred robot jokes, and requested more diverse educational and entertainment activities. They were most risk averse to sharing their conversations with others and information generally with teachers and robot creators. Parents generally thought children would be more open to sharing with the robot than they actually were. Our work suggests co-habitation robots need to incorporate rich narrative-based activities and a wide variety of content to keep children’s attention over time. Their design must incorporate children’s feedback, as parents may not be aware of children’s preferences.

Keywords: In-Home Social Robotics · Long-term Interactions · Information Sharing.

1 Introduction

Robots are becoming increasingly accessible to children and impacting many aspects of their lives, including education [17] and therapy [4]. However, research

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on child-robot interaction often takes place in controlled settings, in part due to a lack of robust robotic platforms that can be studied *in the wild* without researcher supervision. Understanding children’s perceptions of a social robot in their dynamic, everyday environment is necessary to develop context-appropriate technologies. This study, inspired by UNICEF’s *Policy Guidance on AI for children*, aims at understanding children’s voluntary use and perception of child-centered AI and robotics in the natural context of the home [14].

This work builds on previous studies which introduced a table-top social robot *Haru* to children and explored how to align its design with UNICEF’s Policy Guidance, particularly recognizing children’s concerns about privacy when engaging with robots [6]. Since the Haru prototype is still not robust enough for extended home use, here we introduce *Haru4Kids* (H4K), a platform that integrates an app-based avatar of Haru with a table-top rotating stand. H4K was designed to test the feasibility of an in-home social robot for children’s use.

We deployed H4K in the homes of seven families as a pilot study with the following research goals in mind: (1) to identify the *patterns of children’s free use of the robot* over an extended period of time (2 weeks), and (2) to explore the *perceptions of children and caregivers regarding the robot*. This work therefore starts to uncover how a social robot can fit into the dynamics of home life.

2 Related Work: Long-term Adoption of Social Robot Companions

A *co-habiting* robot must establish companionship and foster long-term interactions with children and their families. What defines an interaction as *long-term* depends on the quantity and quality of interactions, the variety of capabilities, and scope of the interaction [1], and when children are no longer perceiving the robot under the influence of the novelty effect [11].

In terms of what makes a fulfilling interaction, children may report hedonic, or pleasurable, reasons for using a robot along with more utilitarian beliefs, such as to study and learn with it [8]. Success can also rely on interesting activities, robot commentary, and immediacy in routines [5]. However, factors that lead to successful interactions can vary depending on children’s individual needs and the presence of parental prompting may help or hurt a child’s motivation for regular interactions [5]. Overall, creating a wide variety of developmentally-appropriate activities can support engaging and long-term child-robot interactions.

Perception of embodied social presence can also affect children’s adoption of social robotic companions [12], and has been found to produce more enjoyable interactions than a virtual agent [16]. Furthermore, expressive motion can influence user perceptions of a robot’s emotions; even a few degrees of freedom can lead users to connect the motion trajectory, intention, and communication of the agent [10]. Our addition of a rotating-tabletop stand elevates the sense of embodiment and social presence of H4K and differentiates our platform from voice-activated assistants like Alexa and onscreen social agents.

3 Methods

3.1 Haru4Kids Platform

The H4K platform consists of a Haru avatar displayed on an iPad supported by a rotating stand (Figure 1a) which spoke using Spanish Text-To-Speech. The app is designed to work on the iPad and uses several Apple-specific libraries. At the highest level of abstraction, the application is divided into seven main modules: User Interface, Conversation Manager, Vision Manager, Central Controller, Settings Manager, Logging, and Stand Manager (Figure 1b). In addition, the Conversation Manager makes use of some services from the *Cloud*. The Central Controller acts as the coordinator of the app behavior, interacting with other modules and accessing the cloud as needed.

Fig. 1: *Haru4Kids*: iPad supported by rotating-tabletop stand and high-level technical description of the system

3.2 Participants

In total, seven families from the South of Spain co-habitated with the robot for two weeks. Consent was collected from caregivers and written assent was collected from children ages 7 or older. Across the participating families, Haru engaged with 14 children ($n_{male} = 9$) between the ages of 6 and 13 ($\mu_{age} = 9.6$). One family had an only child, while the other six families had at least two children. Three families were two-parent households and pairs of parents were interviewed together. In the other four, either single mothers or where parents had shared custody, only the mothers were interviewed (7 caregiver interviews total). Accounting for the periods of time when children were away from the home, such as on vacation or living in multiple households, the robot was in the home for up to an average of 20 days ($\sigma = 5.9$, $\max = 27$).

3.3 Data Collection Instruments

To understand both caregiver and child experiences and concerns with a co-habiting robot, we utilized pre- and post- interviews designed for children and caregivers, and user logs from the app.

Interviews: The interviews blended closed and open questions to collect user’s feedback about *Haru* and understand their comfort with sharing information with and through the robot. In the 30 minute pre-interview, researchers asked children about their first impressions and expectations for interactions with the robot, taking into account that some of the children had experience with the platform in a previous pilot study (e.g. “What are you most excited to try with Haru?”). All family members were all asked to express their comfort levels with keeping *Haru* in different spaces of the home, (e.g., “On a scale from 1 to 7, how comfortable are you keeping Haru in your kitchen?”). These questions were adapted to each family’s space by using a floor plan to visualize the placement of the robot. All members were asked 2 open questions about the space they were most and least comfortable keeping *Haru*. We also asked one multiple-item question about information sharing with a social robot (e.g. “What kind of information would you feel comfortable showing or telling with a robot?”) and 5 questions about sharing information with different third parties through the robot (e.g. “What information would you feel comfortable having the robot share with your teacher?”). All 12 information categories and 5 third parties are referenced in Table 1. Parents were asked about their own comfort with sharing information with the robot, as well as their comfort levels with their child interacting and sharing information with the robot (total of 7 closed, information sharing questions with 12 categories each).

At the end of the trial period, a researcher returned and conducted a 30-45 min post-interview with family members. Adults were presented with 5 likert-style questions about keeping Haru in the home, then 5 open questions about desires from a future, their favorite and least favorite aspects of the co-habitation, and their impression of their children’s favorite and least favorite activities. Children were asked 8 likert-style questions utilizing emoji’s rather than just numbers to identify their excitement about certain activities with Haru. They were also asked 3 open questions to further explore what they enjoyed, didn’t enjoy, or would like Haru to do in the future. As a control, we wanted to see whether the children were perceiving the platform as more than just an on-screen app. Therefore, we asked each participating child to draw Haru from memory. Following these questions, all family members were given the opportunity to answer the same comfort level questions about their home (room-specific) and about information sharing (same 6 or 7 questions for children and adults respectfully)

User Logs: App logs recorded through **Cloudwatch** (from *AWS Cloud*) were used to register the main events (all logins and all interactions with the H4K platform) as they occurred during the execution of the application. No personal information (e.g., images or audio) were stored on the cloud at any moment, respecting the privacy of the children and their families. A detailed

analysis of these logs is out of scope of this paper and will be conducted as part of future work.

3.4 *Haru4Kids* In-home Setup and Activities

Prior to H4K placement, the researcher recorded the pre-interview with at least one caregiver and with each child. Interviews were conducted with parents and children independently to allow them to provide their own feedback. Then, researchers set up the platform in a location specified by the parents. Families were given an explanation of H4K’s capabilities (see below), shown how to quit the H4K at any moment, and set their preferred level of privacy for recording content locally in the iPad. Researchers asked the children to engage with the robot a few times a week and parents were asked to help motivate the children if they were not engaging with H4K on their own.

Once H4K was deployed, the children were greeted with small talk by the robot at the beginning of every interaction. Then, the children could directly ask for an activity, were prompted to play an activity, or the robot chose one at random. This version of H4K features the following is the list of activities:

- **Storytelling:** Once the user selects a story, or H4K randomly chooses one of the seven available, Haru tells the story while displaying related illustrations.
- **Gusano Loco (“Crazy Worms”):** H4K asks the user to suggest a word from within different categories (*e.g.*, colors, shapes, school subjects). After acquiring a list of words, H4K uses them to fill in missing words of an incomplete story and recites the humorous resulting narrative out loud.
- **Detective:** A list of words is given. Within the list there is a word that does not match the others; for example: “apple, *chair*, banana, peach”. The user has to identify which word does not match the rest.
- **Would you rather ... ?:** H4K presents two silly options from which the user chooses which option they prefer (*e.g.*, “Would you rather have three eyes or two noses?”). Once the user has chosen, H4K makes a comment related to their choice, and introduces another scenario.
- **Jokes:** H4K shares three child-friendly jokes in a row.

4 Results

4.1 Takeaways from the Children

General Feedback: All children, regardless of previous exposure to a prototype, had high initial expectations for the robot’s capabilities, such as user recognition, robust dialogues, and legs for playing sports. Of all activities, children interacted with jokes the most (Figure 2a). This aligned with children’s pre-interview answers when asked what they were most excited to try (6 specifically mentioned jokes, 5 mentioned games). Their least favorite part was often the stories (mentioned by 6 participants), with children reporting that the content was repetitive and limited, yet it was the second most frequently started activity across families

Table 1: Child Comfort with Sharing Information.

↓= number of children who changed to discomfort in the post-interview.

↑= number of children who changed to comfort in the post-interview.

Blue = 100% Comfort, Green = $\geq 50\%$ comfortable, Red = $< 50\%$ comfortable

Info Category	General	Third Parties				
		Teacher	Friends	Siblings/ Cousins	Parents	Robot Creators
Third Party		74%	80%	83%	86%	40%
School Grades	57% ↓ ₃	100%	50%	50%	50%	21% ↓ ₃
Hobbies	100%	79% ↓ ₁	100%	93% ↓ ₁	86% ↓ ₁	86%
Conversations with Others	14% ↓ ₂	7% ↑ ₁	14% ↓ ₁ ↑ ₁	14% ↓ ₃ ↑ ₁	29% ↓ ₃ ↑ ₁	14% ↓ ₁
Name	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	42% ↓ ₃
Birthday	86% ↓ ₂	93% ↓ ₁	100%	100%	100%	21% ↓ ₅
Pets	100%	93%	100%	100%	100%	71% ↓ ₁
Family Info	43% ↓ ₁	35% ↓ ₁	50% ↓ ₁	100%	93% ↓ ₁	14% ↓ ₂ ↑ ₁
Friend’s Info	64% ↓ ₃	93% ↓ ₁	100%	50% ↓ ₃	79% ↓ ₂	42% ↓ ₄
Location	43% ↓ ₃	36% ↓ ₁	76% ↓ ₁	100%	100%	21%
Voice Recognition	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	71% ↓ ₄
Face Recognition	93%	100%	100%	100%	100%	42% ↓ ₃
Images of family	57% ↓ ₂	42% ↓ ₃	57% ↓ ₃ ↑ ₁	83% ↓ ₁	93% ↓ ₁	21% ↓ ₂

(Figure 2a). Of all storytelling, 98.5% of stories were chosen at random by H4K rather than requested by the child. Beyond limited content, the biggest reason shared by children for lack of use was disappointment that H4K did not always understand what they said. On average, families used H4K less throughout the second half of the trial period as is represented by the number of recorded verbal interactions expressed by H4K or the user (See Figure 2b).

When asked, children expressed interest in playing with Haru again in their home ($\mu = 6.14$ / (7-point likert scale)). Diverse, interactive activities they suggested for the future included a “Freeze Dance” game, or a board-game like “3-in-a-row.” Children were positive about adding learning components, or a “funny way to study” with Haru, such as receiving math help ($\mu = 5.8$ (7-point likert scale)) and language learning ($\mu = 6.4$ (7-point likert scale)). Many also wanted Haru to be a more holistic companion (e.g. personal alarms to help keep track of time, give advice/a book recommendation, provide recipes for cooking).

In their drawings of Haru from memory, five children drew just the avatar of Haru, one drew the avatar and iPad, one drew just the iPad stand, one drew the stand and the iPad, and six children drew Haru as the integrated stand, iPad and avatar. Therefore, while most interpreted H4K as a holistic platform, there were some children who focused on the the avatar alone.

Information Sharing: The pre- and post- interview allowed us to assess if the children’s comfort with sharing information with a social robot changed after the interactions (Table 1). A paired t-test conducted on the score out of 72 of their comforts, determined that there was a significant difference before and after

Fig. 2: Frequency of activities & Verbal Interactions between H4K and the User

the cohabitation period ($t = 5.303$, $p < 0.001$). The following discuss the specific percentages: only 14% of children felt comfortable sharing their conversations with others with a robot and only 42% of children felt comfortable sharing their location or family information with a robot. The information they felt most comfortable sharing were their name, their pets, and their voice (100%). The third party they felt less comfortable sharing with and were most likely to change their comfort level about were robot creators. See Table 1 for the percentage of children who felt comfortable sharing information with different third parties.

4.2 Adult and Familial Takeaways

General Feedback: Notable benefits mentioned by parents during the post-interview included that their children were spending less time watching TV, were collaboratively playing with H4K and took on a sense of responsibility when establishing sibling turn-taking. However, some parents said it had been a burden to force children to interact with H4K by the end. Others mentioned concern that they were going to break the robot or that it was just another device to keep track of. All parents and most children (71%) felt most comfortable keeping the robot in the living room and most uncomfortable with the idea of keeping Haru in a bathroom. Furthermore, parents were usually able to identify their children’s favorite and least favorite activities with H4K.

Information Sharing: Like their children, adults felt least comfortable sharing conversations with others through Haru (29%). They felt most comfortable sharing their hobbies, birthday, pet information, and friend’s information (all 100%) and their voice (86%). In terms of third parties, adults felt most comfortable with their child sharing information with themselves -the parents- (98%), and the child’s siblings or cousins (89%). They were least comfortable with the child sharing information with the child’s teacher (69%) and the robot creators (67%). However, parents felt comfortable with their children sharing more categories with robots than children were willing to share themselves. Ad-

ditionally, a paired t-test of the adult’s information sharing opinions between pre- and post-test was not significant ($t = 1.387$, $p = 0.22$). Therefore, children were more likely than parents to change their answers post interaction than their caregivers.

5 Discussion

Our study shows that children were open to using a co-habitation robot, though the average number of verbal interactions decreased from the first through the second week. However, the second week of the trial also coincided with the first week of summer vacation, which introduced different family routines and activities. In a future analysis, we will look more closely at sustained use to understand more about how the user engaged throughout each activity.

There are many reasons a family may accept, diminish use, or reject a robot after a co-habitation period of two weeks, including disenchantment, restrictions, and problems with the technology [7]. The expectancy confirmation model [3] can help explain children’s diminished satisfaction and thus disenchantment when initially high expectations are not met. Beyond disenchantment, children’s lack of interest in the stories may have been related to their relevance. The appropriate age was set to the age of home youngest child, so older children’s interests may have been diminished. Additionally, aspects of perception such as perceived competence can stabilize after the first two minutes and can affect long-term attitudes [15] increasing the stakes of first impressions which can be affected by the robot’s aesthetics (e.g. appearance, voice), not just content.

In future deployments, it will be important to mitigate expectations by providing children with transparency statements and adaptable content that can tailor to multiple users’ ages and interests. We are also looking forward to targeting different populations of children who suffer from long-term illness. Beyond being educational and fun for typically-developing children, those with long-term illness can benefit from cognitive tasks that can improve their quality of life [2].

While children might have gained a false sense of security from increased familiarity with the platform [18], our results reveal that children’s preferences for sharing information are not so different from those of their parents, though children’s opinions are more malleable. This supports research that identifies children are increasingly aware of privacy risks, such as cyber risks online [18]. It is also intuitive that the relevancy of the information to the third party aligned with children’s increased comfort with sharing information.

To date there is limited research on children’s concerns surrounding biometric data such as *voiceprints*. However, research identifies that consumers are comfortable with, yet less aware that, they are using biometrics [9]. Some think people may not consider *giving* their voice to the technology the same as giving it to an organization [9]. A high percentage of children were still willing to share their voices with the robot creator (71%). With the expected increase in use of biometric data, child-centered researchers should be transparent about how children’s data are used in the technology. Additionally, it is known that current

child speech recognition is less robust than adult speech recognition [13]. Given children’s disappointment when not understood by the robot and simultaneous comfort with being recognized by their voice, researchers should prioritize developing platforms with robust natural language processing that can disambiguate child speech. It is also imperative to continue developing education for children surrounding personal information privacy with AI.

6 Conclusion

This study reveals that children are excited about the possibilities of a co-habiting robot and may change their comfort with sharing information with the robot and other third parties over time. Overall, Haru4Kids was able to facilitate long-term, productive interactions with children. Our study represents one of few that integrates the experiences of children and their parents throughout a period of co-habitation with a robot. In reflecting on family member feedback, it is important to remember that parents and children are both stakeholders in the adoption of social robots in the home, and taking both of their feedback into consideration is necessary for developing a child-centered robot that will fit into a family context. With this study as a foundation, we are planning to expand the content and length of co-habitation and the number of families involved across countries to compare how the platform performs cross-culturally.

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